

Light-responsive Biowaste-Derived and Bio-Inspired Textiles: Dancing Between Bio-Friendliness and Antibacterial Functionality

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Abstract

Functional antibacterial textiles fabricated from a hybrid of organic waste-derived and bio-inspired materials offer sustainable solutions for preventing microbial infections. In this work, we developed a novel antibacterial textile created through the valorization of spent coffee grounds (SCG). Electrospinning and electrospraying techniques were employed to integrate the biowaste within a polymeric nanofiber matrix, ensuring uniform particle distribution and providing structural support for enhanced applicability. Modification with polydopamine (PDA) significantly enhanced the textile's photothermal performance. Specific attention was paid to understanding the relation between temperature change and key variables, including the

surrounding liquid volume, textile layer stacking, and applied laser power. Developed platforms demonstrated excellent photothermal stability. While the SCG-based textile demonstrated exceptional biocompatibility, the PDA-modified textile effectively eradicated *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*) under near-infrared (NIR) irradiation. The developed textiles in our work demonstrate a dynamic balance between biocompatibility and on-demand antibacterial functionality, offering adaptable solutions in accordance with the desired application.

Keywords: Organic waste valorization, Spent coffee grounds, Micro-Nanostructured textiles, Bio-inspired photothermal agents, Polydopamine, Antibacterial textiles

1 Introduction

The growing challenge of antimicrobial resistance calls for the development of versatile antibacterial strategies that can be tailored to a wide range of environments.¹ These strategies require mechanisms of action that minimize the risk of bacterial adaptation, unlike traditional antibiotic treatments. One approach that aligns with this need is photothermal sterilization.² This method uses a photothermal agent to artificially elevate the targeted surface temperature upon irradiation with light, providing a means to eliminate bacterial contamination. Inorganic nanoparticles with strong light-absorbing properties are effective for photothermal sterilization; however, their widespread application is hindered by cost-inefficiency, production difficulty, and resource sustainability challenges.³ In terms of cost efficiency and resource sustainability, agents derived from biowastes are considered the most promising.^{4,5} Recently, Wang *et al.* created a photothermal agent utilizing a marine biomass hybrid.⁶ The agent displayed potent antibacterial activity with a 99% elimination rate of *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*). Elsewhere, carbon dots were synthesized from the waste pulp of *Citrus limetta* via pyrolysis technique, which showed effective antibacterial activity against both *Escherichia coli* (*E. Coli*) and *S. aureus*.⁷ Recently, a study was conducted to investigate the photothermal properties of spent coffee grounds (SCG) and its potential as a photothermal agent to eliminate planktonic bacteria.^{8,9}

SCG represents a copious by-product of the coffee beverage production process, commonly generated during both coffee brewing and instant coffee manufacturing.¹⁰ The high organic content of SCG contributes to environmental pollution when they are indiscriminately discarded into landfills.¹¹ As such, realizing innovative approaches to mitigate the environmental and economic consequences of SCG accumulation is paramount.¹² SCG contains valuable organic compounds such as hemicellulose, cellulose, lipids, proteins, polyphenols, minerals, and melanoidins.^{13–15} These components, particularly melanoidins, can potentially contribute to the inherent functionality of the platforms derived from SCG. However, most upcycling processes often involve energy-intensive steps or the use of harsh chemicals, which can negate the environmental benefits and increase production costs. To realize the full potential of SCG, an eco-friendly approach should follow a simplified process, reducing costs and environmental impact to make these materials more competitive for large-scale production.¹⁶

The low heat conversion efficiency is a primary issue with biowaste-based photothermal agents.¹⁷ These agents must undergo a complicated purification process that generates

unwanted by-products. Although SCG has some photothermal properties due to the presence of melanoidins¹⁵, its efficiency alone may not be sufficient for applications such as sterilization and antibacterial treatments. Therefore, incorporating a more potent photothermal agent, such as polydopamine (PDA), is a promising approach to enhance photothermal performance and address this limitation. Natural sources containing PDA or melanin inherently fulfill the standards of an effective photothermal agent, including high near-infrared (NIR) absorption and conversion efficiency. In recent years, the excellent photothermal properties of PDA have been exploited in various applications. For example, studies have demonstrated the use of PDA coatings for antibacterial air filters¹⁸ and sterilization of drinking water¹⁹. Combining the abundant nature of SCG and its potential for resource conservation with the robust photothermal properties of PDA, can result in superior performance of the obtained hybrid that may serve as a potent tool for specific applications. Moreover, including PDA into SCG can significantly reduce the necessity of high-temperature carbonization of the biowaste source, leading to substantial savings in energy, time, and labor.

Although the incorporating of the promising photothermal agents like PDA addresses the limitations of SCG's photothermal properties, it is crucial to integrate this combination into a well-defined platform for practical applications. To achieve this, advanced fabrication methods such as electrospinning and electrospraying offer a versatile and straightforward means for creating hierarchically structured materials.^{20,21} During the electrospinning process, a polymer solution is subjected to a high electric field, causing the polymer to stretch into nanofibers and form a fibrous mat.^{22,23} Simultaneously, a suspension of microparticles, exposed to the same high voltage, is sprayed onto the nanofiber mat, becoming embedded within the matrix. These methods provide high repeatability, facile processing, and scaling-up potential, all while enabling precise control over the morphology and composition of the resulting platforms.²⁴

In this study, we have developed a novel approach to fabricate a micro-nanostructured textile by combining SCG particles and polymeric nanofibers through simultaneous electrospinning and electrospraying processes. This approach aims to ensure uniform particle distribution, precise control over particle loading, and provide a well-defined hierarchical structure. To further explore the potential for enhancing performance, the biowaste-based textile was modified with PDA. We carefully assessed the chemical, morphological, and mechanical properties of the micro-nano constructs to confirm both the incorporation of SCG within the nanofibers and the formation of the PDA coating. The photothermal properties of the fabricated textiles were then assessed under NIR irradiation. *In vitro* studies were conducted to explore the biocompatibility of the PAN/SCG textile, highlighting its potential for biomedical applications. Finally, the ability of the modified textile to eradicate *S. aureus* was evaluated. This study highlights the successful valorisation of SCG biowaste into a micro-nanostructured platform offering two distinct functionalities: the PAN/SCG textile demonstrates exceptional biocompatibility, suitable for applications requiring tissue-friendly materials, while the PDA-modified textile exhibits excellent on-demand antibacterial activity under NIR irradiation, making it suitable for applications demanding sterilization or microbial control.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

Polyacrylonitrile (PAN, average Mw 150,000 Da), dopamine hydrochloride, tris hydrochloride (>99% titration, pH 7.0-9.0), and sodium hydroxide (NaOH, >99%) were supplied from Aldrich Chemical Co. and used without additional purification. *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF), ethanol, methanol, and chloroform were purified using standard procedures, stored under molecular sieves, and handled in a moisture-free environment.

Cell culture reagents, including Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM), fetal bovine serum (FBS), penicillin-streptomycin (PS, Gibco Invitrogen), ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA)-trypsin (Gibco Invitrogen), PrestoBlue™ Cell Viability Reagent (Thermo-Fisher Scientific), phosphate buffer saline (PBS, Sigma Aldrich), hexamethyldisilazane (Sigma-Aldrich), paraformaldehyde (Sigma-Aldrich), Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) (Sigma-Aldrich), Alexa Fluor 488 Phalloidin (Thermo-FisherScientific), DAPI (Sigma-Aldrich), and Triton X-100 (Sigma-Aldrich), were used as provided. All chemicals has an analytical grade. A LIVE/DEAD™ Viability/Cytotoxicity Kit assay (Thermo-Fisher Scientific) was also employed. For bacterial studies, *S. aureus* WDCM 00032 ATCC® 6538 was obtained from Argenta. Luria-Bertani (LB) and LB-agar powders were obtained from A&A Biotechnology. Liquid LB medium was prepared by dissolving LB powder (25 g/L) in deionized water and autoclaving at 121 °C for 20 min. LB-agar plates were prepared by dissolving LB-agar powder (40 g/L) in deionized water (Milli Q Water, Millipore), autoclaving at 121 °C for 20 min, and pouring into sterile polystyrene Petri dishes. Sterile 0.1 M phosphate buffer without calcium and magnesium (PBS), pH 7.4, was obtained from Thermo-Fisher Scientific. CCK-8 was obtained from Merck.

2.2 Sample preparation

2.2.1 SCG preparation

SCG was collected from a Costa Coffee outlet in Warsaw, Poland. Before use, the SCG was purified by washing with deionized water (DW) (Milli-Q water filtering system, Millipore, Bedford, MA) to remove potential water-soluble contaminants. The washed SCG was dried at 90 °C for 24 h and then sieved to obtain a consistent particle size distribution below 300 µm in diameter. Size reduction was further achieved through dry and wet ball milling processes. For the wet ball milling mode, ethanol, an environmentally-friendly solvent, was added to the SCG powder to enhance particle dispersion. A concentration of 12% w/v of SCG in ethanol was achieved. Then, the suspension was poured into tungsten carbide milling chambers (250 mL vol.). The milling process was performed in a high-energy planetary ball mill (Fritsch Pulverisette 5). After the optimization process, the following milling conditions were proposed. First, the steel balls of 10 mm diameter were used in BPR 20:1 (ball to powder ratio, where powder means the mass of SCG powder used, excluding ethanol, approx. 25 g per one milling chamber). Then, after 8 h of milling, the steel balls were removed from SCG/ethanol slurry, and 3 mm tungsten carbide balls were used with the same weight ratio. In both steps, the rotational speed of the mill was 200 RPM, and to avoid overheating of the chambers, after every 10 min of milling, 20 min of break was applied. The overall milling time reached 16 h (8 h for

each milling ball diameter). The outcome was a suspension of fine microparticles of SCG in ethanol. This suspension was sealed and stored at room temperature to be utilized for subsequent fabrication steps.

2.2.2 Fabrication of the micro-nanostructured fibrous textiles

Simultaneous electrospinning and electrospraying methods were used to fabricate a nanofibrous textile incorporated with microparticles of SCG. A PAN solution in DMF (11% w/v) was placed in a 1 mL syringe capped with a 20-gauge needle. A similar container held the same volume of SCG suspension in ethanol. Both were subjected to a high voltage of 13 kV, and the flow rate was set at 320 $\mu\text{L/h}$. Experiments were conducted at room temperature and a relative humidity of 20%. The PAN solution's electrospinning was characterized by forming a Taylor cone and, subsequently, a fine jet from the viscous polymeric solution. Simultaneously, the electrospraying of the SCG suspension was observable as a fine spray of particles. A rotary drum with a speed of 500 RPM was employed to collect the SCG microparticles and PAN nanofibers. After approximately three hours, a brownish textile, denoted as PAN/SCG, was achieved with a thickness of approximately 65 μm . Additionally, separate electrospinning of PAN alone was carried out, and the resulting nanofibrous mat was denoted as PAN. All resulting textiles were detached from the aluminum foil and dried in a vacuum oven to remove the DMF residue.

2.2.3 Modification of PAN/SCG with polydopamine

A 0.1 M Tris buffer was prepared by dissolving the Tris hydrochloride powder in fresh DW and stirring until complete dissolution. The pH of the solution was gradually adjusted to 8.5 using 1 M NaOH. After each addition of new volume of NaOH, the pH was evaluated using the pH meter (Mettler Toledo FiveEasy). Subsequently, 20 mL of the Tris buffer was used to soak the micro-nanostructured fibrous textile of PAN/SCG, with dimensions of $8 \times 5 \text{ cm}^2$ and a weight of 50 mg, for 24 h. Afterward, 50 mg of dopamine was added to the vial, and the mixture was stirred for another 24 h. Consequently, the polymerization of dopamine was carried out in the presence of the fibrous textile, and as a result, both the structural materials of PAN/SCG were exposed to dopamine. Later, the coated textile, denoted as (PAN/SCG)@PDA, was thoroughly washed with DW and stored in a sealed container for further studies.

2.3 Spectroscopic, morphological and thermal characterization

To optimize and measure SCG particle size and distribution after milling, a Malvern Mastersizer 3000 particle size analyser with attached HydroMV2000 was used. Approximately, 300-500 mg of SCG suspension was used for each test. The average particle size distribution of SCG powder was obtained from the device. Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) analyses were carried out in attenuated total reflectance (ATR) mode with a Bruker Vertex70 FT-IR spectrometer, and a wavenumber range of $4000\text{--}400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ was recorded with a resolution of 2 cm^{-1} after 12 scans for each sample. The Raman spectra were acquired with LabRam HR800 Raman spectrometer (laser excitation wavelength: 532 nm) (Horiba Jobin Yvon), with the observation of the Raman shifts in the range from $4000 \text{ to } 400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. UV-Vis analyses were carried out for all the textiles in solid state in the diffuse reflectance mode using Perkin Elmer Lambda 1050+ (Madison, WI, USA) supplied from Pro-Environment Polska Sp. z o.o.

(Warsaw, Poland). Measurements were performed in the wavelength range from 200 to 800 nm with the 1 nm per min rate.

All samples were imaged using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) (JSM-6010PLUS/LV, In TouchScope microscope). Depending on the sample, images were taken at different accelerating voltages (7 to 12 kV) and magnifications. X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements of all samples were performed on a Bruker D8 Discover diffractometer using Bragg-Brentano geometry. The analysis was conducted in the angular range of 5-60° (2 θ), with data being collected at each point using a step size of 0.02 per 1.0 s. The thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of the samples (min. 50 mg of powder-like sample) was carried out using Perkin-Elmer TGA 8000 analyzer (Shelton, USA) supplied from Pro-Environment Polska Sp. z o.o. (Warsaw, Poland). The measurement was performed from 35 °C to 800 °C in a nitrogen atmosphere (N₂ was supplied from Air Liquide Sp. z o.o. – Cracow, Poland) with the heating rate 10 °C min⁻¹ and the balance purge flow and the balance purge flow 40 mL min⁻¹.

A CTX Texture Analyzer, Brookfield Ametek, equipped with Texture Pro V1.0 Build 19 software, was used to measure the mechanical properties of the textiles. Samples were cut in a rectangular shape with the size of 4.0 cm by 1.0 cm and secured within the clamps of the device, maintaining a gauge length of 2 cm. Data acquisition occurred at a rate of 50 readings per second. Samples were stretched at a rate of 1 mm s⁻¹ until rupture in triplicates. Young's modulus was derived from the stress-strain curves in the linear elasticity region.

2.4 Assessment of the photothermal properties

The photothermal property of PAN/SCG and its PDA-modified variant was assessed under laser irradiation. A diode laser (Changchun New Industries Optoelectronics Technology Co., Ltd., China) with an 808 nm wavelength was utilized as the NIR light source to irradiate the samples. The laser passed through a set of custom-designed optics, and the final irradiation angle turned 90° from the top. To capture and analyze the spatial heating distribution and temperature profile generated by the laser, a high-resolution infrared camera (FLIR, A655sc) was employed. The camera was equipped with specialized software (FLIR ResearchIR Max), allowing for the recording and subsequent processing of the thermal data collected during the experiments. Circular specimens with a diameter of 9 mm were cut out from textiles, placed in 48-well plates, immersed in different volumes of deionized water (100, 200, and 300 μ L), and irradiated with different laser powers (2.0, 2.5, and 3.0 W). Moreover, to investigate the ability of the NIR laser to penetrate the textiles, different layers (1, 2, and 3 layers) of specimens of the same size were stacked together and placed in wells of a 48-well plate containing 200 μ L of DW.

2.5 *In vitro* cell study

2.5.1 Cell culture

L929 murine fibroblast cells were cultured in DMEM supplemented with 10% FBS and 1% PS. The medium was replaced every 48 h, and the cultures were maintained at 37 °C with a 5% CO₂ atmosphere until reaching 80% confluence. Then, the cells were treated with 0.05% EDTA-trypsin, centrifuged at 1200 RPM for 5 min, and counted. Finally, the cell suspension was diluted in culture media to achieve a seeding density of 10,000 cells per textile sample (Direct test) or 5,000 cells per well (Indirect test).

2.5.2 Direct test: cells seeded on textile samples

Electrospun PAN/SCG and (PAN/SCG)@PDA were cut to the diameter of 1.4 cm. Textile samples were autoclaved and placed in a 24-well cell culture treated plate. L929 fibroblast cells were seeded on the top of the fibrous samples, and the Control of tissue culture plate (TCP, the well without the textile samples) at a density of 10^4 cell cm^{-2} .²⁵ All samples were cultured for up to 7 days.

2.5.3 Indirect test: cells in contact with extracts from textiles

To determine the optimal concentration of (PAN/SCG)@PDA for cell survival and proliferation, the indirect method using ISO 10993-12:2021 standard was applied. The sample extracts from (PAN/SCG)@PDA textiles were prepared as follows: electrospun textiles were cut to match the 6 cm^2/mL standard extraction ratio. The samples were autoclaved and placed in media (DMEM+FBS+PS) for 24 h at 37 °C with a 5% CO_2 atmosphere. Then, the extracts were collected and additionally sterilized using a 0.2 μm filter. Three extract concentrations (100%, 50%, and 20%), diluted in cell culture medium, were prepared to evaluate the optimal concentration of (PAN/SCG)@PDA for cell proliferation. L929 fibroblast cells were seeded in the 96 well-plate at a density of 5×10^3 cells per well. After 24 h, the media was replaced with prepared extracts or pure media (marked as Control).

2.5.4 Cell Viability: Presto Blue™ assay and Live/Dead™ assay

Direct test: A quantitative assessment using the Presto Blue™ assay and a qualitative LIVE/DEAD™ Viability/Cytotoxicity assay was performed to determine the cell proliferation and viability. Fibrous samples and the tissue culture plate (TCP) seeded with L929 fibroblasts were treated with a 10% (v/v) solution of Presto Blue™ Cell Viability Reagent in the culture medium. The samples were incubated for 2 h at 37 °C in a 5% CO_2 environment. Five replicates of each sample were examined with triplicated of each sample at three specific time points: 1, 3, and 7 days after cell seeding. Fluorescence was measured at an excitation wavelength of 530 nm and an emission wavelength of 620 nm using a fluorometer plate reader (Fluoroskan Ascent™ Microplate Fluorometer, Thermo Scientific). A Live/Dead assay was conducted on the 3rd and 7th day of the culture to qualitatively evaluate cell viability. The cells were rinsed with PBS and then incubated for 10 min in a dye solution consisting of 0.5 μL of calcein (to stain live cells green) and 2 μL of ethidium homodimer (to stain dead cells red), dissolved in 1 mL of sterile PBS. After washing the cell samples three times with PBS, they were visualized using a confocal microscope ((Leica TCS SP5 X)).

Indirect test: To investigate the biocompatibility of (PAN/SCG)@PDA textile in more detail, a quantitative PrestoBlue™ assay was applied. L929 cells were seeded on the 96 well-plate and treated after initial attachment to the plate (after day 1) with an extract from the (PAN/SCG)@PDA in the concentrations 100%, 50%, and 20%. The Control L929 samples were treated with normal media.

2.5.5 Cell morphology: SEM and confocal imaging of cell cytoskeleton

The morphology of L929 fibroblasts seeded on the (PAN/SCG)@PDA, and PAN/SCG and TCP were assessed using SEM and confocal microscopy at days 3 and 7 of cell culture. For the SEM imaging, the samples were initially kept in 3% ice-cold glutaraldehyde (Sigma-Aldrich)

for 3 h. Samples were washed three times in DW and dehydrated by immersing them in solutions with increasing ethanol concentrations (50%, 70%, 90%, and 100%) for 15 min each. Subsequently, hexamethyldisilazane (Sigma-Aldrich) was introduced to the constructs, and the samples were air-dried overnight under a fume hood.²⁶ The samples underwent sputter-coating (using II-29030SCTRJEOL SmartCoater) with a thin layer of gold before being analyzed using a SEM detailed in spectroscopic, morphological and thermal characterization section.

For the immunofluorescence staining, samples were washed with PBS and fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde for 15 min at room temperature. After washing, samples were incubated in 0.3% (v/v) Triton X-100 solution for 15 min and then in 1% (w/v) BSA with 0.1% Triton X-100 for 1 hour. Then, the samples were washed and incubated with 1:40 dilution of Alexa Fluor 488 Phalloidin in 1% BSA with 0.1% Triton X-100 for 1 hour in the dark. After washing, the samples were stained with the 1:500 dilution of DAPI in PBS for 10 min. Samples were washed, and cell cytoskeleton and nuclei were visualized using a confocal microscope (Leica TCS SP5 X).

2.6 Antibacterial experiment

2.6.1 Cultivation of *S. aureus* biofilms on (PAN/SCG)@PDA and PAN/SCG

S. aureus WDCM 00032 ATCC® 6538 was used as the model bacteria strain to assess the antibacterial effect of irradiated and non-irradiated (PAN/SCG)@PDA and PAN/SCG. *S. aureus* colonies were stored at 4 °C on solid LB-agar plates containing 10 g/L of tryptone, 5 g/L of yeast extract, 10 g/L NaCl, and 15 g/L of agar (pH 7.0 ± 0.2 at 25 °C). A single bacterial colony was transferred from the agar plate to 2 mL of LB medium consisting of 10 g/L of tryptone, 5 g/L of yeast extract, and 10 g/L NaCl (pH 7.0 at 25 °C). The bacteria were aerobically grown for 5 h at 37 °C on a rotary shaker at 175 RPM. The resulting suspension was diluted with LB medium at a 1:75 v/v ratio and incubated overnight at 37 °C under aerobic conditions at 175 RPM. The OD₆₀₀ of overnight culture was measured using LB medium as a blank. The overnight culture was serially diluted in LB medium until bacteria density reached OD₆₀₀=0.04 ± 0.01 (corresponding to bacteria concentration of approximately 10⁷ CFU/mL). The resulting suspension was 10 times diluted with LB medium to obtain the inoculum (approximate concentration 10⁶ CFU/mL).

Circular samples of (PAN/SCG)@PDA and PAN/SCG were sterilized by autoclaving at 121 °C for 20 min and aseptically transferred to non-treated polystyrene microtiter plate wells. The textile samples were seeded with *S. aureus* inoculum and incubated statically at 37 °C for 4 h to allow cell adhesion. Immediately after seeding the samples, the concentration of bacteria in the inoculum was determined in triplicate using the serial dilution method. After 4 h of incubation, the inoculum was removed from the wells and replaced with 400 µL of LB medium. Positive control wells were prepared identically as the test wells but did not contain samples. The inoculum was introduced into positive control wells for 4 h, after which it was replaced with 400 µL of LB medium. Negative control wells were prepared by adding 400 µL aliquots of LB medium to the wells containing (PAN/SCG)@PDA or PAN/SCG. Test, negative control, and positive control wells were prepared in triplicate. The plate was incubated statically at 37 °C for 46 h.

2.6.2 Irradiation of *S. aureus* biofilms cultivated on samples with NIR

Textile specimens were rinsed with 0.1 M PBS to remove unattached cells, dead cells, and debris before being transferred to a new microtiter plate. 200 μ L aliquots of LB medium were added to the wells containing the textiles. Each sample was irradiated for 20 min with NIR laser with a power of 2.5 W. The irradiation time was optimized beforehand to ensure that the samples remained moist throughout the irradiation. The temperature of the samples during irradiation was monitored using the same setting described in the assessment of the photothermal properties section.

2.6.3 Quantification of viable bacteria on (PAN/SCG)@PDA and PAN/SCG

Viable bacteria on the textile samples were quantified using a modified CCK-8-based method.²⁷ (PAN/SCG)@PDA and PAN/SCG samples including a) samples seeded with *S. aureus* non-irradiated with NIR laser; 2) samples seeded with *S. aureus* irradiated with NIR laser; 3) non-irradiated negative controls (samples cultured in LB medium); 4) irradiated negative controls; 5) positive controls (*S. aureus* suspensions) were rinsed with 0.1 M PBS and transferred to a fresh microtiter plate. 200 μ L aliquots of LB medium and 20 μ L aliquots of CCK-8 reagent were added to the wells containing samples. 200 μ L aliquots of positive control suspensions and 20 μ L aliquots of CCK-8 reagent were added to positive control wells. Additionally, three blank wells were prepared by adding 200 μ L of LB medium and 20 μ L of CCK-8 solution. All samples were analyzed in triplicate. The plate was incubated at 37 °C for 3 h. 110 μ L aliquots were aspirated from each well and transferred to a fresh cell culture-treated microtiter plate. The absorbance of solutions was measured at 450 nm using a microplate reader (Thermo Scientific Multiskan™ GO). The mean absorbance obtained for the blank samples was subtracted from the absorbance readings obtained for the test samples and controls. The viable bacteria on the samples were quantified based on the resulting absorbance readings and the equation derived from the standard curve (absorbance at 450 nm vs. bacteria concentration in CFU/mL, Sup. Fig. 1) by fitting the experimental data points. The percentage of bacteria eradicated from the mat samples during the laser-irradiation (P_{Er}) was calculated according to Eq. 1:

$$P_{Er} = \frac{(C - C_{IR})}{C} * 100\% \quad (1),$$

where C is the average concentration of bacteria on non-irradiated samples, and C_{IR} is the average concentration on irradiated samples.

2.6.4 Verification of the antibacterial effect by direct contact method

The antibacterial effect of laser-irradiated and non-irradiated (PAN/SCG)@PDA and PAN/SCG samples on *S. aureus* biofilms was verified by direct contact method. Immediately after laser-irradiation (irradiated samples) or *S. aureus* biofilm cultivation (non-irradiated samples), textiles were rinsed with sterile 0.1 M PBS and aseptically transferred onto a solid LB-agar plate. Samples were gently pressed against agar and left for 30 s before being removed. Two replicate agar plates were prepared, each imprinted with four mat samples: irradiated (PAN/SCG)@PDA, non-irradiated (PAN/SCG)@PDA, irradiated PAN/SCG, and non-irradiated PAN/SCG. The plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h and photographed hourly. After 24 h, the plates were checked for bacterial growth daily over two weeks

2.6.5 SEM analysis

Non-irradiated and irradiated (PAN/SCG)@PDA and PAN/SCG samples seeded with *S. aureus* were observed under SEM. Non-irradiated samples were fixed with 9% paraformaldehyde at room temperature for 60 min immediately after culture. Irradiated samples were fixed immediately after laser irradiation. Fixed samples were rinsed with 0.1 M PBS and sterile DW and stored at -20 °C until SEM analysis. Before observation, the samples were thawed and dehydrated in aqueous ethanol solutions of gradually increasing concentrations (25%, 50%, 75%, 95%, 99.8%). Dehydrated samples were freeze-dried for two hours and dried at room temperature for 15 min. The samples were then sputtered with gold and observed by SEM, as detailed in spectroscopic, morphological and thermal characterization section.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Fabrication, modification, and characterization of the micro-nanostructured fibrous textiles

Fig. 1a schematically illustrates the preparation process of the micro-nanostructured textile and its subsequent functionalization with PDA. SCG, sourced from a coffee shop outlet, was mixed with ethanol as a green solvent and subjected to a wet ball milling process. This milling step effectively reduced the particle size of SCG to an average of 8 μm and narrowed its size distribution (Sup. Fig. 2), offering several advantages. Firstly, the use of ethanol aligns with eco-friendly practices, promoting sustainability in the fabrication process. Secondly, the smaller and more uniform SCG particles achieved through ball milling are expected to contribute to a final construct with optimized properties such as improved strength and hardness.²⁸ Furthermore, smaller particle size facilitates minimizing energy consumption throughout the fabrication process. Thirdly, the reduction in SCG particle size is crucial for successful electrospaying. Smaller particles are less prone to aggregation and clogging within the apparatus needle, ensuring a consistent and uniform deposition of SCG onto the collector surface. Finally, during the electrospaying process, the rapid evaporation of ethanol from the sprayed charged droplets ensures that dry microparticles of SCG reach the surface. This contributes to well-dispersed particles within the construct and preserves the morphology of the forming platform.

Considering these advantages, we transferred 1 mL of SCG suspension to a syringe capped with a needle. A syringe pump controlled the dispensing of the suspension, and a high voltage was applied to the system. Simultaneously, an equal quantity of a polymeric solution of PAN in DMF (11% w/v concentration) was placed in a syringe and subjected to the same voltage targeted to the collector of SCG microparticles. The SCG suspension remained stable during the electrospaying process, resulting in fine particles of the biowaste being collected on the collector and well-embedded within the PAN nanofibers. Rapid evaporation of the ethanol prevented the formation of macro defects on the nanofibrous platform. After the complete dispensing of the SCG suspension and PAN solution, the PAN/SCG textile was removed from the collector, and any remaining DMF was allowed to evaporate from the construct.

The adopted fabrication process in this study serves several purposes. Firstly, the combination of SCG particles with polymeric nanofibers creates a hybrid material that leverages the unique

properties of both components. Secondly, the topographical cues offered by the micro-nano structure of the matrix can play a crucial role in determining surface characteristics such as roughness and hydrophilicity.²⁹⁻³¹ Lastly, the constraints provided by PAN nanofibers for SCG microparticles significantly enhance the applicability of the biowaste.

To boost the photothermal conversion capability of PAN/SCG, the textile was soaked in a solution of dopamine and Tris buffer. The polymerization of dopamine was allowed to continue for 24 h. Tris buffer has been shown to be an effective modulator during PDA formation.³² The PAN/SCG micro-nano textile maintained the brownish appearance of SCG while the modification with PDA gave it a black color (Fig. 1b). In both cases, the textiles were easy to handle, and their structural integrity was high, demonstrating their robust construction.

To investigate the chemical composition of the textiles upon the incorporation of the SCG microparticles in PAN nanofibers and the further decoration of the nano-micro construct with PDA, FT-IR spectroscopy was employed to analyze the sample spectra. Fig. 1c illustrates the FT-IR absorption spectra, capturing diverse strong, broad, and weak intensities of absorption corresponding to the vast majority of functional groups present in PAN, SCG, and PDA. The FT-IR spectrum of PAN nanofibers displayed the characteristic peaks expected for its chemical structure. Peaks in the range of 2910-2905 cm^{-1} are attributed to the asymmetric and symmetric stretching of C-H bonds in the aliphatic backbone of the PAN structure.^{33,34} A strong peak at 2245 cm^{-1} is the fingerprint for the nitrile ($\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$) stretching vibration, signifying the characteristic pendant group of the PAN polymeric chain. Additionally, the sharp peak at 1668 cm^{-1} , characteristic of the amide I band ($\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretching), suggests either the occurrence of hydrolysis of the nitrile groups during the polymerization process or the presence of residual DMF solvent trapped in the nanofibers.³⁵ The sharp peak at 1452 cm^{-1} as well as the weak peak at 1355 cm^{-1} , correspond to the scissoring vibration of aliphatic $\text{C}-\text{H}_2$ and $\text{C}-\text{H}$ bonds. Finally, peaks around 1250 cm^{-1} and 1100 cm^{-1} indicate the C-C stretching in the PAN backbone and C-N stretching in the nitrile group, respectively.³⁶ When SCG microparticles were incorporated into the nanofibrous structure, changes in the FT-IR spectrum were observed, including gains/losses in peak intensities, shifts in existing peaks, and the appearance of new peaks.

New peaks that emerged at 1740 cm^{-1} and 1040 cm^{-1} , attributed to stretching vibrations of carbonyl and C-O bonds, respectively, are the fingerprints of cellulose and hemicellulose constituents of SCG microparticles.³⁷ The absorption peak of C-H bending from these components overlapped with that of the PAN backbone, intensifying the peak at 1452 cm^{-1} .³⁸ Another characteristic peak specific to the SCG biowaste manifests itself at 1640 cm^{-1} , indicating the presence of lignin through the stretching of $\text{C}=\text{C}$ bonds in its aromatic structure.³⁹ The organic compounds of SCG notably increased the intensity of the bimodal peak between 3000 and 2800 cm^{-1} .⁴⁰ Introducing PDA to the micro-nano architecture further changed the FTIR spectrum. While free (non-surface-bound) PDA would typically exhibit prominent stretching vibrations of phenolic groups (C-OH) around 1278, 1254, and 1238 cm^{-1} , and strong bending vibrations (C-OH) below 1200 cm^{-1} , some of these characteristic peaks either disappear or become significantly weaker in surface-bound PDA.⁴¹ This aligns with the observation that the 1254 cm^{-1} band becomes weak in the (PAN/SCG)@PDA textile, which suggests that the majority of the PDA formed during the synthesis of dopamine in the vicinity

of PAN/SCG, bounded to the surface of either the PAN nanofibers or SCG microparticles and formed a coating. Furthermore, specific to surface-bound PDA, a peak appears at 1508 cm^{-1} , signifying the bending vibration of N-H in the secondary amine of PDA.⁴² A slight shift in the peak associated with the C-OH stretching vibration near 1040 cm^{-1} suggests the formation of hydrogen bonding between the phenolic compounds of SCG's lignin and PDA.⁴³ Moreover, a slight shift to lower wavenumbers in the broad peak from 3100 to 3500 cm^{-1} was detected for (PAN/SCG)@PDA textile, indicative of hydrogen bonding interactions between SCG and PDA functional groups, which suggests good adhesion between these components (Sup. Fig. 3).

To further investigate the structural differences between surface-bound and non-surface-bound PDA, Raman spectroscopy was employed (Fig. 1d). The Raman spectra revealed differences in the structure of surface-bound PDA and PDA particles. For PDA, two characteristic broad Raman peaks at 1377 cm^{-1} and 1597 cm^{-1} , similar to the G and D bands in graphene and graphite are recorded.⁴⁴ The former peak is reported to arise from the aromatic C-N stretching mode of the indole structure⁴⁵, while the latter is recognized to be the fingerprint of C=C aromatic ring vibration. As seen, the intensity of the aforementioned band at 1377 cm^{-1} is low for free or non-surface-bound PDA and increases sharply when this substance is manifested as a coating. This notable difference is reported in other studies.⁴⁶⁻⁴⁸ Ortega *et al.* studied the signal of C-N in PDA by using a 532 nm laser and proposed that a higher number of indole moieties exist in this material when it forms a coating.⁴⁸ It should also be mentioned that as both SCG and PDA have C-N bonds, a synergic effect may contribute to the increased intensity of the 1377 cm^{-1} peak in (PAN/SCG)@PDA.

Finally, the optical properties of the developed textiles were evaluated by UV-Vis diffuse reflectance spectroscopy. The results in Fig. 1e show that PAN nanofibers exhibit strong broadband reflectance across the UV-Vis spectrum, indicating high reflectivity.⁴⁹ According to Snell's Law, light can scatter at interfaces where there is a change in refractive index.⁵⁰ As light interacts with the nanofiber, Mie scattering occurs due to the difference in refractive index between air and the fibers resulting in both reflection and absorption of light. Furthermore, as most nanofibrous textiles have a network of fibers and pores, multiple scattering occurs as light travels in a forward direction. Thicker electrospun platforms, with a hierarchical structure experience increased scattering. This leads to a positive correlation between the platform thickness and both reflectance and absorption.⁵⁰ A significant decrease in the reflectance of PAN is observable with the addition of SCG and also its further modification with PDA. This indicates that the modified textiles absorb more light across the visible spectrum. Moreover, modification with PDA decreases the NIR reflectance (at 800 nm) of PAN/SCG from 70% to 48%, indicating the suitability of PDA as a photothermal agent. The similarities in the reflectance spectra of PAN/SCG and (PAN/SCG)@PDA are likely due to the presence of catechol groups in both SCG and PDA.^{45,51} The color of the platform is another factor influencing reflectance. SCG contains melanoidins, which imparts a brown color.^{15,52} Similarly, PDA forms melanin-like pigments, resulting in dark brown or black hues.⁵³ These darker colors enhance light absorption and contribute to the observed decrease in reflectance in the modified textiles.

Figure 1. Fabrication and modification of the micro-nanostructured textiles. (a) Schematic representation of the fabrication process, including SCG preparation with ethanol-based wet ball milling, simultaneous electrospinning of PAN solution and electrospaying of SCG suspension, and subsequent modification with PDA. (b) Visual appearance of the PAN/SCG (middle) and the (PAN/SCG)@PDA (right). Note the color change after PDA modification and the overall structural integrity of both constructs. (c) FT-IR spectra of the developed textiles, highlighting their characteristic peaks. (d) Raman spectra of PDA particles and (PAN/SCG)@PDA textile, showing the differences in characteristic peaks of surface-bound and non-surface-bound PDA. (e) UV-Vis spectra of the textiles. The fundamental change in the reflectance pattern upon the introduction of SCG and PDA is noteworthy.

The SEM images in Fig. 2a reveal the successful integration of SCG microparticles within the electrospun PAN nanofibrous matrix. At low magnification, the overall micro-nanostructured morphology of the textile is evident, with nanofibers with an average diameter of 830 ± 37 nm forming a mesh-like network. The microparticles of the biowaste appear as irregularly shaped entities, with an average area of $21 \pm 1.1 \mu\text{m}^2$ and an average diameter of $5.5 \pm 0.4 \mu\text{m}$, dispersed throughout the nanofibrous construct. Higher magnification images provide a closer look at the SCG particles, highlighting their rough surface texture. Importantly, the SCG particles appear well-embedded within the PAN nanofibers, suggesting good adhesion and interfacial compatibility between the biowaste and the polymeric matrix. Fig. 2b showcases the morphological changes induced by PDA modification of the PAN/SCG textile. The overall micro-nanostructured architecture is preserved, indicating that the PDA coating process does not disrupt the integrity or porosity of the textile. However, notable differences are observed in the surface characteristics of both nanofibers and biowaste microparticles. A slight increase in average size for both constituents suggests an initial PDA deposition was in the form of a thin coating. Additionally, PDA nanoparticles with an average size of 180 ± 12 nm are observed on the surfaces of both SCG microparticles and PAN nanofibers. Interestingly, PDA appears to have a higher affinity for the biowaste surface, as fibers in the vicinity of SCG do not exhibit a significant size increase or dense population of PDA nanoparticles. This preferential adsorption may be attributed to the presence of catechol and phenol groups in the chlorogenic acid component of SCG.⁵¹ These functional groups can interact favorably with dopamine molecules and promote binding during polymerization. In areas where SCG is sparse, the PDA coating increases the average diameter of PAN nanofibers to 1250 ± 77 nm, forming PDA nanoparticle agglomerates on the fiber surfaces. Furthermore, the images reveal areas where a fusion between PAN nanofibers and SCG microparticles has occurred. This observation suggests that PDA acts as a binder between the textile constituents, creating a conformal coating.

Furthermore, the XRD patterns of PAN nanofibers, PAN/SCG, and (PAN/SCG)@PDA micro-nano fibrous platforms were investigated within the 2θ range of $5\text{--}60^\circ$, as shown in Fig. 2c. The XRD patterns of all textiles exhibited a dominant peak with a maximum intensity at $2\theta=17^\circ$. This peak is characteristic of the semi-crystalline nature of PAN and can be attributed to the (100) crystallographic plane of its hexagonal structure.³⁵ The broadening of this peak suggests a relatively low degree of crystallinity within the PAN nanofibers. Interestingly, the presence of SCG microparticles in the PAN/SCG composite did not cause a noticeable disruption of the PAN structure, nor did it introduce new diffraction peaks specific to SCG.⁵⁴ This may be due to the physically separate deposition of the SCG and PAN components during the simultaneous electrospinning/electrospraying process and the dominance of PAN hexagonal structure diffraction peak effectively masking the characteristic SCG's peak at $2\theta=20^\circ$, corresponding to the (002) crystal plane of cellulose.^{55,56} The very small peak observed at $2\theta=28^\circ$ for PAN and PAN/SCG may indicate a trace amount of a more ordered PAN phase, potentially corresponding to the (110) plane. In the (PAN/SCG)@PDA sample, the addition of PDA introduces two new sharp peaks with low intensities at $2\theta=20.5^\circ$ and 32° . These peaks will likely correspond to the emergence of crystalline domains within the PDA as a thin coating on PAN nanofibers and SCG microparticles.⁵⁷ The peak at $2\theta=20.5^\circ$ could be related to the (002) plane of a stacked, melanin-like structure within PDA.

The results of TGA and DTGA analysis of the biowaste-derived textile as well as its bio-inspired modified variant, are presented in Fig. 2d, enabling the investigation of their thermal stability and composition. Both textiles exhibit similar DTGA patterns with two prominent decomposition peaks. The first peak, centered at around 58 °C, is likely associated with the evaporation of residual moisture trapped within the textile matrix. The sharper and more prominent peak occurring at approximately 305 °C for PAN/SCG and 300 °C for (PAN/SCG)@PDA corresponds to the thermal decomposition of the PAN polymer. The slightly lower decomposition temperature for the (PAN/SCG)@PDA textile may be due to interactions between the PDA coating and the PAN/SCG substrate, potentially influencing the degradation pathways. The mentioned sharp peak at around 300 °C is accompanied by a shoulder, occurring at approximately 350 °C, which can be attributed to the decomposition of lignocellulosic components of the biowaste.⁵⁸ The difference in residual weight at 800 °C is particularly noteworthy. The PAN/SCG textile exhibits a residual weight of 30%, while the (PAN/SCG)@PDA textile shows a higher % residual weight of 37.5%. This difference of 7.5% can be attributed to the presence of PDA, which exhibits higher thermal stability.⁵⁹ Given the reported 56% residual weight for pure PDA particles at 800 °C under nitrogen atmosphere⁶⁰, we can estimate that the (PAN/SCG)@PDA textile contains approximately 13.4% PDA by weight. The quantification of PDA content provides valuable information for understanding the correlation between composition and the resulting properties, such as photothermal performance and antibacterial properties.

Fig. 2e reveals differences in Young's modulus of the PAN, PAN/SCG, and (PAN/SCG)@PDA textiles. Incorporating SCG microparticles increased Young's modulus of the PAN nanofibrous textile from 67.6 ± 25 kPa to 192 ± 50 kPa, a substantial 3-fold increase. This enhancement in stiffness can be attributed to the presence of rigid, well-dispersed microparticles within the polymeric mesh-like matrix, which act as reinforcement fillers. Remarkably, the (PAN/SCG)@PDA textile exhibits the highest Young's modulus (418 ± 90 kPa), surpassing both the PAN and PAN/SCG constructs. This further improvement in mechanical properties suggests a synergistic effect between the SCG microparticles, PAN nanofibers, and the PDA coating. The conformal PDA coating, evidenced by SEM images, closes the gap between the nanofibers and the biowaste microparticles and likely acts as an interfacial bridge, enhancing load transfer between the textile components and improving overall structural integrity under stress.

Figure 2. Morphological, thermal, and mechanical characterization of micro-nanostructured textiles. (a) SEM images of the PAN/SCG, showing the integration of SCG microparticles within the nanofiber matrix, and (b) (PAN/SCG)@PDA, highlighting the PDA coating on the nanofibers and SCG particles, as well as the formation of PDA nanoparticles, at different magnifications. (c) XRD patterns of PAN, PAN/SCG, and (PAN/SCG)@PDA textiles. (d) TGA and derivative TGA (DTGA) curves of PAN/SCG and (PAN/SCG)@PDA textiles, demonstrating thermal decomposition behavior and differences in residual weight. (e) Young's modulus of the textiles illustrates the reinforcing effect of SCG microparticles and the further enhancement in stiffness upon PDA modification.

3.2 Photothermal performance of the organic waste-derived and bio-inspired fibrous textiles

To investigate the photothermal properties of the fabricated textiles, we employed the experimental setup illustrated in Fig. 3a. This setup allowed us to monitor the temperature changes of the PAN/SCG and (PAN/SCG)@PDA textiles in real-time under NIR laser irradiation. The presence of both lignin and melanoidins within the SCG biowaste and the PDA surface modification are expected to contribute to the overall photothermal conversion capability of the textile platforms.

Lignin, a key component of SCG, exhibits photothermal properties due to its structure comprising aromatic rings and conjugated functional groups.^{61,62} Electrons within these systems transition to excited states upon absorbing light energy. The subsequent non-radiative relaxation of these electrons back to the ground state releases energy in the form of heat. Similar to lignin, both melanoidins and PDA possess intrinsic photothermal properties stemming from their complex chemical structures and broadband absorption characteristics.^{63,64} PDA

disordered polymeric network, comprised of indolic and phenolic units, enables the absorption of light across a wide range of wavelengths. Upon excitation, the rapid non-radiative relaxation of electrons from excited states to the ground state releases energy in the form of heat. Melanoidins, with their conjugated aromatic rings, exhibit a similar mechanism. The presence of these aromatic systems promotes the transition of electrons to an excited state (π^*) upon light absorption. As they relax back to the ground state, a significant portion of the absorbed energy is dissipated as heat. These characteristics highlight the potential of both PDA and melanoidins as potent photothermal agents (Fig. 3a).

Fig. 3 b-d are dedicated to the photothermal behavior of PAN/SCG, and Fig. 3 e-g depict that of (PAN/SCG)@PDA under different conditions, namely the applied laser power, surrounding liquid volume and textile layer stacking, respectively. It should be noted that during the assessment of the textiles' photothermal performance, the platforms were completely surrounded in an aqueous medium in all aforementioned conditions to simulate environments with high moisture content, such as wounds, biomedical devices in contact with bodily fluids, industrial settings, or biofouling scenarios.

The temperature change of the PAN/SCG textile had a direct correlation with the NIR laser power (Fig. 3b). A maximum of 33 °C ΔT was recorded when the laser power was 3 W and the textile was immersed in 200 μL of DW. The lowest NIR power tested in our study was 2 W, which yielded 26 °C of ΔT after 20 min of irradiation.

Upon irradiation with an NIR laser with a power of 2.5 W, a circular piece of PAN/SCG fabric containing approximately 0.5 mg of the biowaste can heat up 200 μL of DW to 47.5 °C starting from room temperature (20 °C) in less than 6 min (Fig. 3c). This measure happens faster when the fabric is under 100 μL (3 min) and slower when immersed in 300 μL (15 min) of DW. After 20 min of irradiation, a ΔT of 31 °C was achieved. A previous study,⁸ showed that to achieve the mentioned ΔT at such conditions, a SCG solution with a concentration of 90 mg/mL was needed. This is remarkable considering the area of the PAN/SCG textile and the laser power used in our study (2.5 W, 0.64 cm²). It demonstrates the effectiveness of the fabrication method in creating a well-dispersed micrometer-sized organic waste-derived photothermal agent in a nanofibrous textile. As expected, when the laser is turned off, the elapsed time needed for cooling to room temperature is proportional to the volume of liquid surrounding the fabric.

Similar to the volume of the coolant and the power of the NIR laser, the mass of the photothermal agent is another factor determining the extent of the released heat and the subsequent changes in temperature. As the SCG is well dispersed and fixed among the PAN nanofibers, and therefore direct manipulation of its quantity in a fabricated textile is not possible, we evaluated the mentioned factor by stacking different layers of PAN/SCG to simulate the changes in the amount of SCG. Fig. 3d shows the temporal profiles of stacked layers of PAN/SCG response to a 2.5 W NIR laser when immersed in 200 μL of DW. While the presence of one layer can increase the water temperature to 51 °C from room temperature, 3 layers of PAN/SCG can generate a 51 °C ΔT after 20 min of irradiation. This was expected, as by increasing the number of layers, more SCG is exposed to the laser beam, and therefore a higher temperature can be reached after a specific time of irradiation. However, it seems the mentioned changes do not follow a linear path. This can be attributed to each layer contributing to the shielding of the NIR laser, diminishing the ability of the beam to reach the photothermal

agents located further from the laser source. This observation highlights the importance of optimizing textile layering for real-world applications to ensure efficient light penetration and maximum photothermal conversion.

To study the photothermal behaviour of (PAN/SCG)@PDA, the determining factors in heat generation were re-evaluated. A responsive trend in temperature increase was observed when the (PAN/SCG)@PDA textile was subjected to different NIR powers (Fig. 3e). A 3.0 W NIR laser could increase the temperature to 73 °C while, at the same time, 2.0 W of power raised the temperature of DW to 63 °C. Considering that the achieved ΔT for NIR laser powers of 2.0, 2.5, and 3.0 W was 43, 48, and 53 °C, respectively, it can be said that the temperature increase has a linear correlation with NIR power for the PDA-modified textile.

Fig. 3f shows the temporal profiles of the PDA-modified textiles immersed in different volumes of DW. Remarkably, one layer of (PAN/SCG)@PDA was able to totally evaporate 100 μL of DW in less than 17 min upon being subjected to 2.5 W of NIR laser power. This exceptional performance highlights the potent photothermal conversion capabilities of the PDA-modified textile. The same laser power could increase the temperature to 68 °C when the volume of DW was 200 μL . The stored latent heat of DW was released upon turning off the NIR source, and the textile demonstrated an excess of 100 s of delayed cooling when the volume increased to 300 μL .

Fig. 3g shows the effect of PDA mass on the heat generated by photothermal conversion, resulting in the temperature change. The concentration of the bio-inspired agent in one layer of (PAN/SCG)@PDA when immersed in 200 μL of DW is approximately 0.7 g/L (data derived from the TGA results). Two layers of such textile, stacked together and irradiated with NIR power of 2.5 W, can raise the temperature of the medium to 78 °C. Surprisingly, the addition of a third layer did not contribute to photothermal conversion, and the maximum achievable temperature remained unchanged. Therefore, it can be deduced that two layers of the (PAN/SCG)@PDA textile are sufficient for effective shield the NIR laser beam.

As a comparison, the temporal plots of PAN, PAN/SCG and (PAN/SCG)@PDA textiles, irradiated under a 2.5 W NIR laser for a duration of 20 min while immersed in 200 μL of DW, are presented in Fig. 3h. The photothermal conversion efficiencies of PAN/SCG and (PAN/SCG)@PDA textiles were determined to be $20.60 \pm 0.85\%$ and $37.19 \pm 1.03\%$, respectively, demonstrating that the PDA coating significantly enhances the photothermal performance of the developed textiles (Supporting information, Table S1). The mentioned medium volume and the laser power were selected for the antibacterial studies. It should be noted that the photothermal behavior of the developed textiles was also briefly studied in dry mode (Sup. Fig. 7). It was revealed that the rise in temperature upon turning on the NIR laser is almost instantaneous. Incredibly high temperatures of 140 °C and 90 °C can be achieved for (PAN/SCG)@PDA and PAN/SCG, respectively, after only 5 s of NIR irradiation. This rapid heating capability suggests potential applications for these textiles in areas where fast, localized temperature increases are desirable.

Furthermore, to assess the thermal stability of the textiles, an uninterrupted irradiation test was conducted, and related profiles were plotted (Fig. 3i and j). During this test, PAN/SCG and (PAN/SCG)@PDA immersed in 200 μL of LB medium were exposed to seven consecutive

irradiation cycles, each composed of 10 min with the NIR laser "on" at the fixed power of 2.5 W, followed by 10 min with the laser "off" to cool the medium back to room temperature. The temperature maxima during each irradiation cycle showed minimal deviation, indicating excellent photothermal stability for both textiles. This stability is likely a result of the robust nature of the organic waste-derived and bioderived photothermal agents, as well as efficient heat dissipation within the fibrous matrix of the textiles. The capability to re-irradiate these textiles multiple times without compromising their photothermal properties greatly broadens their potential applications across sectors that demand recurrent heating or sterilization cycles while maintaining cost-effectiveness.

Figure 3. Photothermal properties of micro/-nanostructured textiles. (a) Schematic of photothermal experiments with textiles in a multi-well plate, temperature changes captured by thermal imaging, and temperature plot displayed in real-time. Inset: proposed photothermal mechanisms of PDA and melanoidins, the photothermal components of the textiles. Structural representations are adapted from

the works of Hematpour *et al.*⁶⁵ (PDA) and Bruhns *et al.*⁶⁶ (melanoidins). (b-d) Photothermal behavior of PAN/SCG textile under varying conditions: (b) NIR laser power, (c) surrounding liquid volume, (d) textile layer stacking. (e-g) Photothermal behavior of the (PAN/SCG)@PDA textile under varying conditions: (e) NIR laser power, (f) surrounding liquid volumes, (g) textile layer stacking. (h) Direct comparison of the photothermal response of PAN, PAN/SCG and (PAN/SCG)@PDA textiles under the same conditions. Photothermal stability of (i) PAN/SCG and (j) (PAN/SCG)@PDA textiles was evaluated through seven consecutive cycles of NIR irradiation and cooling.

3.3 *In vitro* studies of the developed textiles

To assess the suitability of the developed textiles for biological applications, the *in vitro* biological response was evaluated by examining the viability and proliferation of L929 fibroblasts. A schematic overview of the employed direct and indirect cell culture methods is provided in Fig. 4a. During the direct contact culture, cells were seeded on PAN/SCG, (PAN/SCG)@PDA, and a TCP as a Control over a 7-day culture period. The PAN/SCG textile demonstrated remarkable biocompatibility. Quantitative studies of cell proliferation confirmed these observations (Fig. 4b). Further studies (Sup. Figs. 8, 9) revealed the abundance of healthy cells on the PAN/SCG surface. In the case of (PAN/SCG)@PDA, L929 cells did not adhere to the textile during seeding. This observation suggests that while the PDA modification enhances photothermal properties and is suitable for on-demand antibacterial applications, it may affect the surface characteristics of the textile, potentially influencing cell adhesion. An indirect exposure culture test was conducted to investigate the impact of the PDA modification further. The tests revealed that at lower concentrations, extracts from the (PAN/SCG)@PDA textile exhibit improved biocompatibility (Fig. 4c).

Overall, *in vitro* studies showed that cells adhere readily to the surface of PAN/SCG, proliferate, and eventually form multi-layered colonies, after 7 days of incubation, as visualized in Fig. 4d and Sup. Fig. 10. The live/dead staining (Fig. 4e) and confocal imaging (Fig. 4f) further highlighted the presence of adhered, spindle-shaped fibroblasts on the PAN/SCG textile, confirming its excellent biocompatibility.

The exceptional biocompatibility of the PAN/SCG textile supports its potential for a variety of biomedical applications. The favorable interaction between fibroblasts and the biowaste-derived textile suggests its suitability for promoting wound healing processes. This finding opens possibilities for its use as wearable fabric and wound dressing.

Figure 4. *In vitro* biocompatibility evaluation of micro-nanostructured textiles. (a) Schematic illustration of the direct and indirect cell culture methods employed to assess the biocompatibility of the PAN/SCG and (PAN/SCG)@PDA textiles. (b) Direct test: Quantitative analysis of L929 fibroblast cell proliferation on the PAN/SCG, (PAN/SCG)@PDA, and TCP (Control) over 7 days of culture. (c) Indirect test: Quantitative analysis of L929 fibroblast cell viability when exposed to different concentrations (100%, 50%, 20%) of extract from the (PAN/SCG)@PDA textile for 7 days, with untreated cells serving as a control. (d-f) from direct test: (d) SEM, (e) Live/Dead staining (green – live cells, red – dead cells), and (f) Confocal image (stained with DAPI for nuclei – blue, and Actin for cytoskeleton visualization – green) of L929 fibroblast spreading on the PAN/SCG textile after 7 days of culture.

3.4 On-demand eradication of bacteria from the developed textiles

Having comprehensively assessed the photothermal properties of the developed organic waste-derived and bio-inspired textiles, their on-demand antibacterial potential was evaluated. Fig. 5a schematically illustrates the experimental setup, where *S. aureus* bacteria were cultured on PAN/SCG and (PAN/SCG)@PDA textiles and subsequently exposed to NIR laser irradiation. To determine bacterial survival, both irradiated and non-irradiated textiles were contacted directly on agar and cultured for 24 h. In parallel, bacterial viability was quantified using a detection kit.

Fig.5b shows the growth of *S. aureus* on agar plate imprinted using direct contact method with circular PAN/SCG and (PAN/SCG)@PDA textile samples irradiated and non-irradiated with NIR laser at two time points. The results revealed excellent bactericidal properties of (PAN/SCG)@PDA against *S. aureus* under NIR irradiation. No bacterial growth on agar over the area imprinted with laser-irradiated (PAN/SCG)@PDA sample was detected. The lack of bacterial growth was sustained over 2 weeks, confirming complete biofilm eradication and textile sterilization. In contrast, the areas of agar imprinted with non-irradiated PAN/SCG and (PAN/SCG)@PDA samples showed unrestricted bacterial growth, completely covering the exposed area with a bacterial lawn within 24 h. Irradiated PAN/SCG samples demonstrated a mild antibacterial effect, resulting in a delayed onset of bacteria growth compared to non-irradiated samples. However, after 24 h, the area imprinted with the PAN/SCG samples was fully covered with *S. aureus* lawn, similar to the coverage formed after imprinting agar with non-irradiated samples.

These findings were further confirmed through the quantitative analysis of biofilm eradication (Fig. 5c). Upon 20 min of irradiation, the textile was sterilized entirely. Mature *S. aureus* biofilms cultivated on (PAN/SCG)@PDA with a total of $6.42 \pm 0.239 \times 10^8$ cells were completely eradicated with 100% efficiency in all analyzed samples. The antibacterial effect of (PAN/SCG)@PDA was directly related to its strong photothermal properties, as previously discussed. PAN/SCG had only a slight antibacterial effect that led to the eradication of only $15.30 \pm 5.28\%$ out of $1.023 \pm 0.031 \times 10^9$ cells forming the bacterial biofilm on the samples.

The direct contact method and the quantitative analysis collectively revealed no growth of *S. aureus* on the laser-irradiated (PAN/SCG)@PDA. Although PAN/SCG exhibited a slight antibacterial effect upon laser-irradiation, it could not prevent bacterial growth significantly. SEM images of biofilms grown on both (PAN/SCG)@PDA and PAN/SCG (Fig. 5d and Sup. Fig. 12, respectively) revealed bacterial cells infiltrating the porous structure of the textile, with multicellular grape-like clusters embedded in an amorphous extracellular matrix (ECM), indicating high proliferative cell activity. Upon NIR irradiation, (PAN/SCG)@PDA showed severe destruction of bacterial biofilms, resulting in the complete elimination of bacterial cells with residues of acellular ECM covering on and around nanofibers and microparticles (Fig. 5d). In contrast, bacterial cells colonizing PAN/SCG were only partially eradicated. Clearly visible round-shaped ruptures in the ECM indicate areas where cell death occurred. At the same time, numerous viable cells with well-preserved round morphology typical of staphylococci remained visible within the micro-nanostructured construct after laser irradiation (Sup. Fig. 12). SEM results indicate that the photothermal and sterilizing effects of (PAN/SCG)@PDA can be

attributed to the presence of PDA on the surface of PAN nanofibers and SCG microparticles. At the same time, the organic waste-derived textile alone does not exhibit a significant antibacterial effect.

Considering that the dense extracellular matrix of most bacterial biofilms creates a significant diffusion barrier impeding the penetration of chemical antimicrobial agents and antibiotics, the photothermal mechanism of bacteria eradication exhibited by (PAN/SCG)@PDA may prove a more effective way of removing microbial biofilms. The photothermal mechanism ensures strong, uniform bactericidal action throughout the entire volume of the sterilized material, making it particularly valuable for porous matrices with highly developed internal surfaces.

Figure 5. On-demand antibacterial properties of micro-nanostructured textiles. (a) Schematic representation of the *S. aureus* bacterial culture setup on PAN/SCG and (PAN/SCG)@PDA textiles, followed by NIR laser irradiation and subsequent assessment of bacterial survival. (b) Agar plates showing imprints of irradiated and non-irradiated PAN/SCG and (PAN/SCG)@PDA textiles after 3 and 24 h of culture. Complete suppression of bacterial growth is observed for the irradiated (PAN/SCG)@PDA textiles. (c) Quantitative evaluation of the antibacterial effects of laser-irradiated and non-irradiated (PAN/SCG)@PDA and PAN/SCG textiles on *S. aureus*. (d) SEM images of (PAN/SCG)@PDA textile cultured with *S. aureus* before and after NIR laser irradiation. The characteristic grape-like clusters of *S. aureus* observed before irradiation are absent after irradiation, with only residues remaining.

4. Conclusions

In this study, we successfully valorized SCG into a functional micro-nanostructured textile platform. The electrospinning and electrospaying processes ensured uniform SCG distribution within a matrix of PAN nanofibers, providing structural integrity and enhanced applicability. The use of a green solvent and the minimal intervention required for SCG processing emphasizes the sustainability aspect of the developed platform. Modification of the PAN/SCG textile with PDA significantly enhanced its photothermal performance. In general, PDA and SCG particles, rich in lignin and melanoidins, contribute to enhanced photothermal conversion efficiency and broad-spectrum light absorption. Meanwhile, the polymeric nanofibers provide stability to the platform, ensuring its practical application and potential for large-scale production. Detailed characterizations confirmed successful textile fabrication and demonstrated exceptional PAN/SCG textile biocompatibility, highlighting its potential for a range of biomedical applications. PDA potent photothermal conversion properties combined with the highly porous nature of micro-nanostructured (PAN/SCG)@PDA resulted in excellent antibacterial properties capable of completely eliminating bacterial biofilms. These features are especially desirable from the standpoint of medical and industrial applications requiring material reuse while maintaining high cleanliness levels or multiple sterilization cycles, such as medical protective equipment sterilization, sustainable water purification, or wastewater treatment systems.

Author contributions

Seyed Shahrooz Zargarian: conceptualization, validation, resources, investigation (Textiles fabrication, SEM, FTIR, photo-thermal characterization, drug releases, ESR tests), methodology, writing – original draft, writing – review & editing, supervision, project administration, funding acquisition. Barbara Kupikowska-Stobba: validation, investigation (*in vitro* antibacterial), methodology, writing – original draft, writing – review & editing. Alicja Kosik-Kozioł: validation, investigation (*in vitro* cell studies), methodology, writing – original draft, writing – review & editing. Magdalena Bartolewska: investigation (optical characterizations), methodology, writing – original draft, writing – review & editing. Anna Zakrzewska: investigation (mechanical tests), methodology, writing – original draft, writing – review & editing. Daniel Rybak: investigation (textile modification and XRD), methodology, writing – original draft, writing – review & editing. Kamil Bochenek: investigation (SCG ball milling and particle size analysis), methodology, writing – original draft, writing – review & editing. Magdalena Osiał:

investigation (TGA and UV-Vis in solid state), methodology, writing – original draft, writing – review & editing. Filippo Pierini: review & editing, supervision, project administration, funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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